

Microhabitat Dynamics of *Euphorbia caducifolia* and Its Influence on Herbaceous Plant Communities

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Abstract: Semi-arid regions of the Aravalli foothills experience harsh climatic conditions that limit plant establishment and growth. *Euphorbia caducifolia*, a drought-tolerant succulent shrub, plays an important role in modifying local microhabitats. The present study analyses the influence of *E. caducifolia* on herbaceous plant communities in the Pushkar–Ajmer region. Vegetation sampling was conducted under shrub canopies and in adjacent open sites, accompanied by soil nutrient analysis. The results show that canopy-covered microhabitats have improved soil moisture, higher organic carbon, and greater herbaceous species richness compared to open areas. These results support the stress-gradient theory which states that positive plant interactions increase under stressful conditions (Bertness & Callaway, 1994; Maestre et al., 2009). *E. caducifolia* acts as a nurse shrub that facilitates herbaceous diversity and may be used in ecological restoration of degraded rangelands.

Keywords: Microhabitat Dynamics, *Euphorbia caducifolia*, Herbaceous Plant Communities, semi-arid landscapes.

1. Introduction

The Pushkar–Ajmer foothills of the Aravalli Range represent a semi-arid ecosystem characterized by low rainfall, high evaporation rates, and nutrient-poor soils. Vegetation in such habitats is predominantly composed of drought-tolerant shrubs and seasonal grasses. Plant–plant interactions play an important role in such landscapes, particularly under environmental stress conditions (Pugnaire & Luque, 2001). *Euphorbia caducifolia* Haines is a characteristic xerophytic shrub of the region. Its clump-forming growth pattern can influence the microenvironment by providing shade, reducing wind velocity, and trapping litter, thereby modifying soil properties (Flores & Jurado, 2003; Padilla & Pugnaire, 2006). These modifications can enhance the growth and diversity of herbaceous plants beneath its canopy.

2. Study Area

The study was performed in the foothill regions around Pushkar and Ajmer in Rajasthan, located between 26.45° N and 74.60° E. The climate is semi-arid, with an average annual rainfall of 400–550 mm, mainly during July–September. The soils range from rocky and gravelly slopes to sandy loams in valleys. Dominant shrub species include *Euphorbia caducifolia*, *Capparis decidua*, *Ziziphus nummularia*, and *Acacia senegal* (Singh & Rathore, 2014; Gupta & Sharma, 2013).

3. Species Description

Euphorbia caducifolia is a perennial, leafless succulent shrub with green photosynthetic stems. It contains latex and propagates both vegetatively and by seed. The shrub commonly forms clumps and serves as a soil stabilizer, reducing erosion and forming localized fertile patches (Tewari, 2000).

4. Materials and Methods

Sampling was conducted during the post-monsoon season (August–October). A total of 40 quadrats (1×1 m) were laid, 20 under *E. caducifolia* canopies and 20 in adjacent open areas. Herbaceous species were recorded for density, frequency, and cover. Soil samples (0–15 cm depth) were analyzed for moisture, organic carbon, pH, available nitrogen, and available phosphorus.

5. Results

Table 1: Comparison of soil and vegetation characteristics under shrub canopies and in open sites

Parameter	Under <i>E. caducifolia</i> (Average)	Open Site (Average)
Soil Moisture (%)	7.2	5.3
Organic Carbon (%)	0.55	0.36
Soil pH	7.6	7.8
Available Nitrogen (kg/ha)	185	145
Available Phosphorus (kg/ha)	11.5	8.7
Herb Species Richness (per m ²)	14–15	7–8
Shannon Diversity (H')	2.2	1.5
Herb Biomass (g/m ²)	210	130

Table 2: Common Herbaceous Species Observed

Group	Species
Grass	<i>Cenchrus ciliaris</i>
Grass	<i>Cenchrus setigerus</i>
Grass	<i>Dactyloctenium aegyptium</i>
Grass	<i>Chloris barbata</i>
Grass	<i>Eragrostis minor</i>
Herb	<i>Indigofera cordifolia</i>
Herb	<i>Alysicarpus monilifer</i>
Herb	<i>Tephrosia purpurea</i>
Herb	<i>Boerhavia diffusa</i>
Herb	<i>Celosia argentea</i>
Herb	<i>Tridax procumbens</i>
Herb	<i>Achyranthes aspera</i>
Herb	<i>Phyllanthus maderaspatensis</i>
Herb	<i>Senna tora</i>

6. Discussion

The improved soil properties and higher herbaceous diversity under *E. caducifolia* indicate its role as a facilitator species. This supports the stress-gradient hypothesis, which predicts increased facilitation in harsh environments (Bertness & Callaway, 1994; Maestre et al., 2009). Similar facilitative effects of shrubs on herbaceous vegetation have been observed in other semi-arid ecosystems (Flores & Jurado, 2003; Padilla & Pugnaire, 2006). Therefore, *E. caducifolia* can be used as a functional species for restoring degraded rangelands in the Aravalli foothills.

7. Conclusion

Euphorbia caducifolia modifies soil conditions and enhances herbaceous plant diversity in the Pushkar–Ajmer foothill region. Its role as a nurse plant makes it valuable for ecological restoration and land rehabilitation in semi-arid landscapes.

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